

Masalalarni yechishda zanjirli kasrlarning qo`llanilishi

Qurbonaliyeva Shoira Maxmanazarovna

SamDCHTI akademik litseyi matematika fani bosh o`qituvchisi

shoiraqurbonaliyeva839@gmail.com,

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada akademik litseylar algebra va analiz asoslari darslarida masalalarni yechishda zanjirli kasrlarning qo`llanilishi haqida nazariy bilim va bu bilimni mustahkamlashda yangi pedagogik texnologiyaning “Moslik o`rnating” usulidan foydalanib “O`zingizni sinab ko`ring” ruknida topshiriqlar berilgan .

Kalit so`zlar: Zanjirli kasr, “Moslik o`rnating” usuli.

Davlat rahbari hurmatli prezidentimiz Sh. Mirziyoyev tomonidan jadal rivojlanish uchun “to`rtinchi sanoat inqilobi” kasblarining ahamiyati qayd etildi. Shu munosabat bilan, yoshlarni matematika (STEM) bilan bog`liq kasblarga qiziqishini o`stirish zarur. O`quvchilarning intellektual qobiliyatlarini jadal o`stirishda, ularning chuqur, tabaqalashtirilgan va kasb-hunarga yo`naltirilgan bilim olishlarini ta`minlash nuqtai nazaridan kelib chiqib ushbu maqolani yozishga “bel bog`ladik”.

Ushbu maqola yoshlar uchun sifatli ta`limni ta`minlashda, iqtidorli yoshlar qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda, shuningdek, umumta`lim maktablari , akademik litseylarda faoliyat yuritayotgan aniq fanlar metod birlashmalarida o`rganib chiqilib, darslarda foydalanilsa, albatta, ta`lim sifati oshishida yordam beradi degan umiddamiz.

Masalalarni yechishda zanjirli kasrlarning qo`llanilishi

Matematika masalalarini yechishda ayrim qiziqarli tenglamalarga kelib qolamiz. Shunday tenglamalardan biri Diofant tenglamalaridir. Diofant tenglamalarini yechishning bir qancha usullari bor. Bu ishda Diofant tenglamalarni zanjirli kasrlar yordamida yechishni keltiramiz.

$$a + \frac{b_1}{a_1 + \frac{b_2}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{b_n}{a_n}}} a + \frac{b_1}{a_1 + \frac{b_2}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{b_n}{a_n}}} \quad (1)$$

Ushbu

$a_i (i = \overline{0, n}), a_i (i = \overline{0, n}), b_j (j = \overline{1, n}) b_j (j = \overline{1, n})$ butun sonlar ko`rinishidagi ifoda uzluksiz zanjir deyiladi. Agar (1) da $b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = \dots = b_n = 1$, $b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = \dots = b_n = 1$, $a_0 a_0$ butun son $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots a_n a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots a_n$

lar natural sonlar bo‘lib, $a_n > 1, a_n > 1$ bo‘lsa, u holda ushbu

$$a + \frac{b_1}{a_1 + \frac{b_1}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{b_n}{a_n}}} a + \frac{b_1}{a_1 + \frac{b_1}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{b_n}{a_n}}}$$

ifoda **chekli zanjir kasr** deyiladi.

$$+ \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{2}}}} + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{2}}}}$$

Masalan: 3 ifoda chekli zanjir kasrga misol bo‘ladi. Bu zanjirli kasr

$$+ \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{2}}}} = 3 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{2}{9}}} = 3 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{9}{20}} = 3 + \frac{20}{29} = \frac{107}{29}$$

3

$$+ \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{2}}}} = 3 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{2}{9}}} = 3 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{9}{20}} = 3 + \frac{20}{29} = \frac{107}{29}$$

noto‘g‘ri kasrning bir ko‘rinishi

$$\frac{107107}{2929}$$

bo‘lib, uni [3;1,2,4,3] belgi orqali ham berish mumkin. Bu belgi noto‘g‘ri kasrning zanjirli kasrga o‘tish belgisidir.

1-misol. $\frac{a}{b} = [-1; 1, 2, 4, 5] \frac{a}{b} = [-1; 1, 2, 4, 5]$ zanjirli kasrga mos kasrni toping.

$$\frac{a}{b} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{5}}}} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{5}{21}}} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{21}{47}} = -1 + \frac{47}{68} = -\frac{21}{68}$$

Yechish:

$$\frac{a}{b} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{4 + \frac{1}{5}}}} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{5}{21}}} = -1 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{21}{47}} = -1 + \frac{47}{68} = -\frac{21}{68}$$

Javob: $\frac{a}{b} = -\frac{21a}{68b} = -\frac{21}{68}$

2-misol. $\frac{1972}{1508} = [1; 3, 4] \frac{1972}{1508} = [1; 3, 4]$ kasrni zanjirli kasrga yoyish yordamida qisqartiring.

$$\frac{1972}{1508} = 1 + \frac{1}{3 + \frac{1}{4}} = 1 + \frac{4}{13} = \frac{17}{13}$$

Yechish. Kasrni zanjirli kasrga yoyamiz:

$$\frac{1972}{1508} = 1 + \frac{1}{3 + \frac{1}{4}} = 1 + \frac{4}{13} = \frac{17}{13}$$

Javob: $\frac{1972}{1508} = \frac{17}{13} \frac{1972}{1508} = \frac{17}{13}$

3-misol. Berilgan $\sqrt{15}\sqrt{15}$ sonini zanjir kasr ko‘rinishida ifodalang.

$$\sqrt{15} = 3 + \frac{1}{a_1}\sqrt{15} = 3 + \frac{1}{a_1};$$

Yechish.

$$a_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6} = 1 + \frac{1}{a_2} a_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6} = 1 + \frac{1}{a_2};$$

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6}-1} = \frac{6}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{6 \cdot (\sqrt{15}+3)}{6} = \sqrt{15} + 3 = 6 + \frac{1}{a_3}$$

$$a_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6}-1} = \frac{6}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{6 \cdot (\sqrt{15}+3)}{6} = \sqrt{15} + 3 = 6 + \frac{1}{a_3};$$

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}+3-6} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6} = 1 + \frac{1}{a_4}$$

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}+3-6} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6} = 1 + \frac{1}{a_4};$$

$$a_4 = \frac{1}{\frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6}-1} = \frac{6}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{6 \cdot (\sqrt{15}+3)}{6} = \sqrt{15} + 3 = 6 + \frac{1}{a_5}$$

$$a_4 = \frac{1}{\frac{\sqrt{15}+3}{6}-1} = \frac{6}{\sqrt{15}-3} = \frac{6 \cdot (\sqrt{15}+3)}{6} = \sqrt{15} + 3 = 6 + \frac{1}{a_5};$$

$a_4 = a_1$ $a_4 = a_1$ bo'lganligi uchun, yana yuqoridagi jarayon hosil bo'ladi.

Demak, $\sqrt{15} = [3; (1,6)]\sqrt{15} = [3; (1,6)]$ cheksiz zanjirli kasrni hosil qilib, uning taqribiy qiymatini topamiz.

$$\sqrt{15} = 3 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{6+\dots}}\sqrt{15} = 3 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{6+\dots}}$$

Javob:**4-misol.** $[2; 1, 1, 6, 8]$ zanjirli kasrga ko'ra sonning o'zini toping

$$2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{6+\frac{1}{8}}}} = 2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{8}{49}}} = 2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{49}{57}} = 2 + \frac{57}{106} = \frac{163}{106}$$

Yechish. $[2; 1, 1, 6, 8]=$

$$2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{6+\frac{1}{8}}}} = 2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{1+\frac{8}{49}}} = 2 + \frac{1}{1+\frac{49}{57}} = 2 + \frac{57}{106} = \frac{163}{106}$$

Javob: $\frac{163}{106}$ $\frac{163}{106}$.

5-misol. $\frac{2222}{106}$ kasr $[2; 1, 3, 4, 1, 2]$, $[0; 3, 1, 2, 7]$, $[0; 1, 1, 6, 8]$, $[-3; 1, 1, 2]$ zanjirli kasrlarning qaysi biriga mos?

Yechish. Avvalo masala shartini o'qib, tahlil qilamiz. Berilgan kasr to'g'ri kasr bo'lganligi uchun uning butun qismi 0 ga teng. Demak, biz yechimni $[0; 3, 1, 2, 7]$ va

[0;1,1,6,8] zanjirli kasrlar ichidan izlaymiz. Ularni zanjirli kasr ko`rinishida yoyib, shakl almashtirishlar bajarganimizdan so`ng natijaga erishamiz.

Javob: [0;3,1,2,7]

Aziz o`quvchi, keling pedagogik texnologiyani "Moslik o`rnating" usuli orqali yuqorida olgan bilimlarimizni mustahkamlab olaylik. Zero, takrorlash -bu bilimning onasidir.

O`zingizni sinab ko`ring

Topshiriq:	Moslik o`rnating:	Javoblar:
$\frac{a}{b} = [2; 1,1,3,1,2]$ $\frac{a}{b} = [2; 1,1,3,1,2]$ zanjirli kasrga mos kasrni toping.		$\frac{58}{21}$
$\frac{2494}{903} = [2; 1,3,5]$ $\frac{2494}{903} = [2; 1,3,5]$ kasrni zanjirli kasrga yoyish yordamida qisqartiring.		[3;(1,2,1,6)]
Berilgan $\sqrt{14} \sqrt{14}$ sonini zanjirli kasr ko`rinishida ifodalang.		$\frac{64}{25}$
[3;1,1,2] zanjirli kasrga ko`ra sonning o`zini toping		[0;1,4,3,2]
$\frac{3030}{3737}$ kasr qaysi zanjirli kasrga mos?		$\frac{18}{5}$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

1. Alimov Sh.A., Kolagin Yu.M. va boshqalar. "Algebra va analiz Asoslari". O`rta maktabning 10-11 sinflari uchun darslik. -T.: "O`qituvchi", 1996 - y.
2. Abduhamidov A.U., Nasimov X.A., Nosirov U.M., Husanov, "Algebra va matematik analiz asoslari". I qism. Akademik litseylar uchun darslik. - T.: 2008y.
3. J.Husanov, X.A.Nasimov, N.B.Shamsiddinov, M.Do`stmurodov . "Algebra", I qism, Akademik litseylar uchun darslik.- T.2023y